

SMART URBAN MOBILITY APPLICATION IN SAN SEBASTIAN CITY

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Abstract: Nowadays, mobility is one of the main individual and social needs; mobility demand is growing especially in urban areas, where it is strongly related to the number of people needing public transportation. Mobility problem in cities is currently dealt from an intermodal approach, using different modes of transport, and enhancing efficiency of public transport and urban environmental quality. The goal of this paper is to present a mobile application for smart management and analysis of multimodal mobility in urban environments, concretely in San Sebastian city. This application aims to offer a multimodal and flexible real time solution that allows the user to select the best way to move within the city in each time.

Keywords: E-hitchhiking, park&go, real time multimodal mobility solution.

Introduction

Companies involved in providing mobility for the masses play an essential role in the energy and environmental sectors: 30% of the energy consumptions of a highly developed country is associated with transport systems. Comparatively, in Europe transport systems are responsible for 25% of all CO₂ emissions. On the other hand, today 64% of all kilometers made are urban and this data is expected to triple by 2050. Being able to get around urban areas quickly, conveniently and with little environmental impact is critical to their success.

The goal of this paper is to present a mobile application for smart management and analysis of multimodal mobility in urban environments, concretely in San Sebastian city. This application is based on a platform that aims to provide citizens with flexible information about several forms of multimodal transport, integrating several services of added value and real time adaptability to their needs and circumstances.

On the other hand, real data extraction for mobility studies development is implemented, so that it can be a feedback for the generation of a mobility and sustainability research

General overview of mobility management in Gipuzkoa/San Sebastian

There are currently several isolated initiatives that promote sustainable mobility in the city of San Sebastian. Each of them is oriented to a concrete line of action:

- Bikes: a public bicycle network is available to citizens in different parts of the city. It initially consists of 9 stations, having 195 parking spots for a total of 150 bicycles.
- Pedestrian environment: the number of pedestrian streets and pedestrian areas is increasing, in favour of mobility in the city. Moreover, the construction of mechanical vertical mobility mechanisms to respond to problems of accessibility is a solution that is gaining increasing importance.
- Public transport: Currently there are 27 lines serving the city and communicating daily the different neighbourhoods of San Sebastian.
- Other initiatives promote the use of biofuels, bus services to work places, information to the traveller, personalized transport plans, car sharing systems, etc.

Taking all this into account, the main problem is that all these initiatives are unconnected and the user notices the lack of information as a prior necessity. So, there is a need of a mobile application that not only integrates all the modes of transport as well as additional information that allows managing the urban mobility, but also provides an adapted solution to the user due to his/her restrictions and needs in real time.

SUMA, an application for urban mobility management in San Sebastian

SUMA (Smart Urban Mobility Application) is a new mobile application for smart urban mobility management and analysis developed for the city of San Sebastian (Spain). This application is oriented to smartphones, and allows users to integrate all mobility alternatives and combinations among them in real time, so that they can select those more convenient for the current necessities and create their personal multimodal mobility solution. SUMA is based on 4 main pillars: electronic hitchhiking (DriveMe application), bikes management tool,

- Electronic hitchhiking
- Bikes management tool
- Park&Ride tool
- Urban public transport real time information

They are independent modules that can work as separate components and they can also be interconnected for the generation of the multimodal solution to the user. One of the aims of the app is to be as open as possible to be able to accept new more components in the future.

This enables the user to configure the software with preferences such as the desired transport modes to include.

SUMA architecture

The core component of the architecture [Figure 1] is based on two main elements; the user

terminal with Android OS and with internet connexion in order to access to the services provided by the service platform, and the service platform in the control center, containing the database and the web services that allow to access to the database and the repositories of the transport operators.

Figure 1. Architecture of SUMA platform

The user terminal or smartphone includes:

- An internal GPS identifying the user positioning.
- GSM/GPRS/3G connexion to the service platform, in order to exchange required data
- HMI for the user to access the functionalities of the application
- QR reader application for the passenger validation.

The service platform includes following services:

- To manage the requests related of each of the modules integrating SUMA application
- To access to GIS OSM (Open Street Map) data and to the OTP (Open Trip Planner) route generator and OMQ (Open Map Quest) for the generation of the public transport routes and the private routes and for the visualization of them.
- To access to the public transport data of considered operators
- To manage the users database
- To run specific algorithms, such as passenger finding algorithm, driver finding algorithm or multimodal planner algorithm.

External data considers the next:

- GIS: for the route calculation and visualization GIS is required. OSM database is considered for this purpose, since it totally fits SUMA application requirements.
- Public Transport Information: For the modules of public transport information and park and ride module, external data access is required. These repositories are available through the website of both the San Sebastian municipality and the transport operators.

The interface between the back office and the external data has two different parts. The part oriented to obtain the static data is made through GTFS (Google Transit Feed Specifications) available for the region. On the other hand, access to dynamic data is made through some dedicated web services specifically developed for this purpose that aims to extract the data independently of the operator that owns it

Main functionalities of SUMA application are described next:

Electronic hitchhiking

The main application of SUMA is DriveMe, which basically consists on a dynamic private car pooling, where a car driver aims to share his free seats with other users with compatible mobility requirements. It is usable not only for scheduled trips but also for those that receive on real time demand. A punctuation system is used for the rating of both driver and traveller, so that it can be taken into account when choosing colleagues for travelling. On the other hand, routing algorithms have been implemented and included in the application, so that original routes can be slightly modified to provide service to other users and make them optimal.

The main options offered to the user are:

- Offering free seats in my car: the driver publishes required parameters related to his personal profiles and to the trip to realize, including the “extra-time” which accept for the route in case that it allows other users to share it. Once this data is sent to the server, the implemented algorithm looks for those passengers that fit with the published data. This result is shown to the driver, who can check the new generated route on the map and the profile of each proposed passengers. If the driver accepts one of them, the suggestion is sent to the passenger, and acceptance is required for closing the expedition. The selected passenger will receive a notification of this pendant confirmation.
- Asking for free seats in a car: a passenger can also publish the route aimed to make, including some required parameters. The implemented algorithm finds for those drivers who could share their free seats according to the restrictions imposed. The result of the algorithm is shown to the passenger so that he can check the driver’s profile and score and accept or reject the offer. If it is accepted, the driver will have to confirm also his willingness to share his car with that passenger.
- Consulting my trips: each user can consult his trips, represented by different icons. Those trips where the user is a passenger can have following states:
 - o Closed trip (identified by a QR code icon): a driver has been already confirmed for that trip. The passenger has the QR code for identification when the trip starts.
 - o Open trip (identified by a lens): it has not been found any drivers that fits with

the passenger requirements. When this trip is selected, the algorithms automatically starts with the search of an accurate driver.

- To be confirmed trip: a driver has already received a request, but it has not been confirmed yet.

On the other hand, those trips where the user is a driver are identified with a car icon, and an arrow which redirects to another screen that shows all the details of the trip over a map.

Figure 1 Screenshots of DriveMe application

Bikes management tool

This tool aims to offer real time information to the users about the availability of the bikes along the several anchor points, which is a very useful functionality when riding and aiming to park the bike. This tool includes the following services:

- Map with the bike lanes network of the city. The bike lanes, known as “red ways”, are connected creating a network that permits travelling by bicycle without sharing the roads with the cars.
- Localization of the bike-hire points and bike parking points. Apart from the hiring points, a list of public bike parking areas already exists in the city.
- Routing algorithm to travel along the bike lane network. It creates the best route to go from one point to another.
- Status of the bike-hire points, indicating. the number of free slots and number of available bikes.

An occupancy-based flexible fare system for the bike-hire points can be expected in the near future to achieve automatic bike redistribution. This option allows the system manager to consider variable rates for the rental, so that the redistributive task is relieved. Messages containing information about flexible rates are pushed to the users through SUMA application

in real time when the redistribution is urgent.

Park&Ride tool

Assuming that the use of the private car becomes unavoidable in many scenarios when accessing the city from small town where other collective transportation services are limited, SUMA application aims to help drivers in choosing the best location to park a car.

This tool offers real time information about the location, occupancy and general information of the parking areas in the city, and also allows the user to combine the trip with public transport to reach the final destination. This tool offers to the user georeferenced position of all car-parks within the city: park and ride, underground and surface car parks and related information, such as opening hours, pricing, available spaces

Urban public transport real time information

All these mobility modes require the combination with public transport modes information, since this is the most sustainable mode of motorized transport in urban environments nowadays.

In the last few years, an important administrative effort is being made in the region in order to make transit information publicly available.

Information related to lines of different operators, connections among them and an algorithm to calculate how to reach a destination from the actual position of the user are offered through the application.

Multimodal mobility solution approach

In some cases, the best solution for the final users goes through the right combination of different modes of transport, so that it can fit their actual needs and mobility requirements. In this sense, one of the options provided by SUMA tool is the generation of a multimodal solution that considers user restrictions prioritizing sustainable modes of transport.

Mobility and sustainability analysis tool

A key factor in the development of successful mobility policies is the knowledge of the real demand. Therefore, in the SUMA project, a mobility and sustainability analysis tool is designed to quantify the actual user requests according to days of week and several travel preferences. This is aimed to provide an important feedback to planners about the actual needs of users. The data extracted from the platform may be used for studies and statistics in order to detect and help predict present and future trends in urban mobility

Developed algorithms

The main algorithm developed is a routing and driver/passenger suggestion algorithm and

runs in the following situations:

- A driver publishes a route; possible passengers are searched and offered to him/her.
- A passenger publishes a request; possible drivers suitable to cover that request are searched.
- When a driver or passenger asks for a new search, any time after the publication.

The basics of the route calculation are the driver parameters. From the original journey and time, a base route is created with a maximum deviation accepted by the driver (extra kilometers and time). The direct path from two geographical positions (driver origin and destination) is retrieved using OpenMapQuest API, which also returns the estimated time, and the distance. All this information is stored in the table “Itineraries” in the database.

From a given passenger request the system performs the next steps:

1. From the database, get the list of the driver itineraries (travelling still alone, or with other passengers already assigned) that satisfy seat and time restrictions (+/- 30 minutes).
2. For each itinerary in that list, the ordered stops sequence is extended with two new stops (passenger’s origin and destination) and the end of the sequence.
 - 2.1.The Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP) “optimized route” of the OpenMapQuest API is called again with this new sequence. The result must be analyzed by the SUMA algorithm, because TSP problem does not solve all the Pickup and Delivery Problem (PDP) constraints of the e-hitchhiking scenario. This is done in the following steps.
 - 2.2.Check if origin stop from each passenger is visited before that user’s destination stop.
 - 2.3.Check the accumulative sum of passengers at each stop on the itinerary. The sum of all the passengers that get on in previous stops minus the sum of all the passengers that get off in previous stops must never exceed the number of offered seats.
 - 2.4.If steps 2.2 and 2.3 are valid, new time deviation is checked against driver’s maximum accepted deviation. If this is valid, the new temporal itinerary is added to the solutions list.
3. For efficiency and to avoid providing users with a long list, the algorithm is stopped once 5 possible solutions are found, and found driver options are shown to the passenger.

If the algorithm is run beginning from a driver publication, instead of a list of driver itineraries, passenger requests are retrieved from the database, and steps from 2.1 to 2.4 performed for each one. The solutions list will contain a list of possible passengers that are shown to the driver in order to choose one if desired so.

A route is found to be definitive once both driver and passengers have confirmed it. If any of

the passengers has not confirmed the changes on a journey in a given time, the previous accepted itinerary will be performed.

A notifications system has been included in order to assure the communication between final users. Each time an itinerary has an update that affects other users, they get notified. A QRCode is transmitted to all the passengers to be used at getting on the car, to confirm that they have correctly met the driver.

Algorithms for the automatic redistribution of the bikes according to the level of occupancy of each parking spot are under construction.

Conclusions

Several institutions have shown their interest in this project; AVIA service station network has made available to SUMA a cumulative point system. These points are the currency for the users of DriveMe application and can be exchanged by fuel. On the other hand, during the months of May and June 2013, real trials will be developed in the Technology Park of San Sebastian, which has also shown real interest in SUMA application, since workers travel every day using different modes of transport, with the priority use of the private vehicle. It is expected that the use of SUMA application can be a solution for parking problems, as well as congestion after work.

An important contribution for the integration of different modes of transport is expected with the SUMA application, not only regarding the multimodal combination of public transport services, but also including a responsible use of the private car. Moreover, the possibility to extract real demand data provides a powerful tool to evaluate and quantify both service quality and user needs.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the Municipality of San Sebastian who contributed and helped to develop this project, in order to achieve a more sustainable mobility in the city. On the other hand, this work was partially supported by Basque Government (call Gaitek 2011).

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